

SOFTWARE-BASED ANALYSIS OF PROGNOSTIC COMPETENCIES OF PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekistonda ta'lim tizimining hozirgi holati, ta'lim tizimining rivojlanish tendentsiyalari ko'rib chiqiladi. O'qituvchining kasbiy faoliyatni malakali bajarishi uchun zarur bo'lgan pedagogik mahoratining tarkibi ochib berilgan. O'qituvchining kasbiy kompetensiyasini shakllantirish zarurati allaqachon mutaxassisni kasbiy tayyorlash bosqichida namoyon bo'ladi. O'qituvchining boshqaruv faoliyatini samarali amalga oshirish uchun zarur bo'lgan shaxsiy fazilatlar asoslanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: kompetentsiyalar, o'qituvchining boshqaruv kompetentsiyasi, quyi sinf o'qituvchisining boshqaruv kompetensiyasi tarkibi, o'qituvchining kasbiy muhim fazilatlar, o'qituvchining shaxsiy fazilatlar.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены современное состояние системы образования в Узбекистане, тенденции развития системы образования. Раскрывается состав педагогических умений, необходимых для профессиональной деятельности педагога. Необходимость формирования профессиональной компетентности педагога проявляется уже на этапе профессиональной подготовки специалиста. Обоснованы личностные качества учителя, необходимые для эффективной управленческой деятельности.

Ключевые слова: компетенции, управленческая компетентность учителя, структура управленческой компетентности учителя младших классов, важные профессиональные качества учителя, личностные качества учителя.

Abstract: The current state of the education system in Uzbekistan, trends in the development of the education system are considered in the article. The composition of the pedagogical skills necessary for the professional performance of the teacher is disclosed. The need to form the professional competence of the teacher is already manifested at the stage of professional training of the specialist. The teacher's personal qualities necessary for effective management activities are based.

Key words: competencies, teacher's managerial competence, structure of lower grade teacher's managerial competence, important professional qualities of the teacher, personal qualities of the teacher.

INTRODUCTION

After analyzing the scientific literature and identifying the important feature of the concept of prognostic competence (hereinafter - PK), we understand the personal skill aimed at independent knowledge of the problem formed in the process of prognostic activity. Willingness to solve and apply acquired knowledge, educational abilities and skills, as well as methods of working in life in solving practical and theoretical problems, personal program in future elementary school teachers in transitional conditions the formation model was

developed. Formation of Prognostic competence in future primary school teachers should be considered innovative in the context of modernization of the educational process.

Prognostic competence is a component of specialist training, in other words, it is fundamental in the formation of professional competence. The problem of predictive competence and the development and formation of competence is considered in various theoretical approaches (V.D. Shadrikov and others) and in a number of dissertations: Prisyajnaya A.F. Borisova Z.N. Prognostic competence is analyzed from the point of view of synergistic approach.

If a primary school teacher has prognostic knowledge, skills and abilities, is an active and independent thinker, can solve various problems creatively, he can organize the educational process in a way that meets the requirements of modern society. Especially, in our opinion, this applies to the training of future primary school teachers. Readiness for prognostic activity allows solving professional and educational problems in further professional and pedagogical work at the scientific level.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Various models of prognostic competence formation have been studied.

A model is a form of knowledge about the surrounding world, an information equivalent of an object built for specific practical purposes. The urgency of creating a model of predictive competence formation in primary school teachers is related to the transition of secondary vocational education to new state educational standards, the essence of which is the formation of general and professional competencies.

The Model of Prognostic Competence Formation in Future Primary School Teachers serves as a guiding and coordinating role and is designed to reflect the characteristics, qualities and abilities that we predict for future primary school teachers, as individuals. forms the basis of Prognostic competence. and the life activity gives a positive result for the subject, society and the future.

RESULTS

The basis for creating a predictive competence formation model includes:

1. A competency-based approach based on a number of principles:

- focus on the development of educational and professional motivation, self-development and self-improvement;
- directing the student to independently choose a profession in a certain direction for deeper learning;
- connection with real production (solving specific tasks based on the needs of city enterprises);
- use of active forms and methods of teaching;

2. System-activity approach based on a series of ideas (A.N. Vygotsky, V.V. Galperin, D.B. Leontiev, P.Ya. Elkonin):

- ideas of consistency;
- development is possible only through activity;
- focus on results;
- the idea of integrity, which implies the interdependence, interaction and integration of all components of the school education system.

3. Axiological approach (E.V. Bondarevskaya, V.A. Slastyonin, V.S. Lednev) (the main rules for us are the following):

- Vocational education is given to develop the value consciousness of the future specialist. Value consciousness and self-awareness are anchored in a person's value orientations;
- Based on the directions of professional value, the future specialist can build a model of his activity, which will become a guide for his self-development and improvement.

Analyzing the different classifications of the main competences, we focused on the ideas of I.A. Zimnyaya, and therefore we can connect the prognostic competence to the person, as a person, as a subject of vital activity, and competences related to human activity.

Stages of formation of Prognostic competence of primary school teacher.

Stages (preparation (stage 1) - aimed at activating the student's need for prognostic activity, eliminating initial tension;

Procedural and activity (transformation) (stage 2) - transformation - is characterized by the fact that the idea acquires the actual-search character of self-awareness for students

(3rd stage) - conducting research within the framework of classroom and extracurricular activities, gathering personal solutions to problem groups, analyzing diagnostic methods, work on the topic of self-education; field seminars with the demonstration of seminars and presentations on the studied problem of research participants in other educational institutions, etc.); analytical and corrective

(Step 4) - the subject of review and modification is its own research activity from its own point of view.

Based on the important features of the personal program, we have isolated a certain set, a system of personal qualities, which serve as criteria for the formation of Prognostic competence and ensure its successful solution of professional and life problems in standards.

DISCUSSION

The following components and criteria have been determined for the formation of a personal program.

1. Motivational value - reflects readiness to demonstrate competence. The main criterion is awareness and motivation for the specific content of research activities (specially organized conditions - educational discussions, propaedeutic courses, game learning, modular learning), all of which form the active position of the student as a researcher. Valuable attitude to the chosen profession.
2. Cognitive component (view of the world) - forms a system of knowledge about nature, society, thinking, techniques, methods of activity, their assimilation ensures the formation of a scientific view of the world in the minds of students.
3. Content - indicates the possession of the content of competence, that is, the formation of personal qualities that constitute an integral characteristic of a person. Criterion: readiness of students for research activities;
4. Behavioral component - reflects the experience of demonstrating research competence in various standard and non-standard situations.
5. Relational component - attitude to the content of research competence. The main criterion is the level of formation of reflexive skills.

Thinking is a unique human ability that allows you to make yourself the subject of review (analysis and evaluation) and practical change.

The following are the principles of organizing the model:

- the unique value and uniqueness of the student's personality;

- The connection between the technology of IC formation and the stages of professional development of a person;
- to direct professional education to the student's individual research experience;
- integration.

CONCLUSION

This model of the formation of prognostic competence in primary education specialists includes a system of criteria that allows determining the level of possession of this type of competence: imitative-passive level (weakly expressed psychological preparation for independent cognition, independent prognostic activity is imitative). ; the level of active research is characterized by the sufficient formation of prognostic activity in students, the system of knowledge and skills necessary to perform interpretative (heuristic) prognostic activity, to know the logic of research actions is formed; intensive creative level. characterized by the formation of a high level of psychological preparation for prognostic activity (motives of activity independence and value orientations are clearly expressed), independent creative research experience is available and accumulated, their approaches, the logic of their thoughts, their own ability to solve problems there is the creation of a strategy, which leads to self-improvement of actions and activities in general. The criteria for the formation of predictive competence correspond to the stages of the formation of predictive competence in elementary school teachers.

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